

UDC 377: 811.111

DOI: 10.15587/2519-4984.2021.241191

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED ENGLISH LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN SPEAKING IN FUTURE SPECIALISTS OF HOTEL AND RESTAURANT BUSINESS

Iryna Skril

Methodological approaches to the formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant specialists are selected and revealed, and the principles of this process are substantiated. The essence and structure of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking of future specialists of hotel and restaurant business are formulated. The preconditions of vocabulary use, including terminological, are considered. It has been found, that the production of oral speech is impossible without the perception and understanding of oral speech by ear. The following approaches are described, which provide methodical and methodological substantiation of the process of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future specialists of hotel and restaurant business, such as: communicative, interactive, student-centric, sociolinguistic. The peculiarities of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future specialists of hotel and restaurant business on the basis of the communicative approach are outlined. The educational materials, used in the application of the communicative approach, are investigated. The interactive discourse, which is a type of communicative activity, is considered. The principles, on which this process is based, are analyzed: general methodological principles (situational; communicative activity; communicative value; immersion), specific principles speech clichés, parallel activation of visual and auditory channels of information perception). Recommendations for the optimal combination of classroom learning and extracurricular learning, including independent work with the help of network technologies using video, audio and text materials, are given. Learning outcomes are formulated on the basis of the student-centered approach, attention is focused on students' skills and competencies. On the basis of the sociolinguistic approach, the creation of educational situations for the purpose of reproduction of scenarios of professionally oriented communication of experts of hotel and restaurant business is provided. It is concluded, that the formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant professionals on the basis of communicative, interactive, student-centric, sociolinguistic approaches will ensure the effectiveness of this process

Keywords: *communicative, interactive, student-centered, sociolinguistic, professionally oriented lexical competence in speaking, principles*

How to cite:

Skril, I. (2021). Methodological approaches to the formation of professionally oriented english lexical competence in speaking in future specialists of hotel and restaurant business. ScienceRise: Pedagogical Education, 5 (44), 15–22. doi: <http://doi.org/10.15587/2519-4984.2021.241191>

© The Author(s) 2021

This is an open access article under the Creative Commons CC BY license hydrate

1. Introduction

Globalization processes of the twentieth century caused the dynamic development of international tourism. The condition of society necessitates the improvement of professional qualifications of specialists who will work in the field of tourism, especially in the field of hospitality services, which is one of the most promising sectors of the tourism business. Since their performance of their roles and professional responsibilities focuses mainly on oral communication with clients and colleagues, the formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant professionals becomes a priority for their foreign language training in HEIs.

T. Dudley-Evans, N. Mykytenko, O. Petraschuk, C. Wrangham-Briggs, M. St John, O. Tarnopolsky, A. Waters, T. Hutchinson, L. Chornuvat and others de-

voted their scientific works to the problems of teaching English for special purposes. Peculiarities of teaching professionally oriented English speaking to specialists in various fields were studied by Y. Avsyukevich, O. Babyuk, I. Zadorozhna, I. Kodlyuk, N. Lyamzina, I. Fedorova, V. Chernysh. The formation of lexical professionally oriented competence has become the subject of scientific research, in particular by N. Zhovtyuk, A. Kotlovsky, Y. Semenchuk, V. Tereshchuk, A. Tomashevskaya.

The arsenal of approaches to the formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant professionals determines the goals of learning the vocabulary in the process of speaking as a type of speech activity.

The methodology is based on the main objectives of foreign language teaching, including practical, devel-

opmental, general education and upbringing. The selected goals outline the process of formation of language competencies (in particular, lexical) in the context of learning speech activity (in particular, speaking).

The formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant professionals is a complex process, the understanding of which should be carried out from different positions. Communicative, interactive, student-centric, sociolinguistic approaches are chosen as the methodological bases of the researched object.

2. Literary review

The process of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking requires the definition of theoretical foundations for the definition of target competence. Scholars in domestic periodicals cover the problems, associated with the disclosure of the essence and structure of lexical competence. Thus, Anna Vorobets in her article "The concept of "lexical competence" in modern methods of teaching foreign languages" analyzes lexical competence as a component of communicative competence [1]. However, she points out the problem of free operation of foreign lexical units and their use in a real context. Accordingly, English lexical competence should be included in both the linguistic and speech components of communicative competence. Therefore, it is very important to understand, that the content of a foreign language is related to the knowledge of the vocabulary of a foreign language. O. Polyanichko in the article "Components of the content of lexical competence of future history teachers" defines lexical competence as a complex formation, which includes: motivational, cognitive, activity-practical, reflexive and behavioral components [2]. The formation of lexical competence is proportional to the formation of students' lexical skills. It is advisable to highlight the principles of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking, including future professionals in hotel and restaurant business. The work of N. Mykytenko and A. Kotlovsky "Intercultural communication as a condition for the formation of foreign language professional and communicative competence of future specialists in non-philological specialties" substantiates the effectiveness of intercultural communication as a condition for the formation of foreign language professional and communicative competence [3]. It was found, that the components of intercultural competence are knowledge, skills, abilities, empathy, flexibility, cross-cultural awareness, ability to overcome stress, high level of foreign language proficiency, situational factors. But the issues related to communicative situations during the formation of English lexical competence in professionally oriented speaking in future hotel and restaurant professionals remained unresolved.

The formation of professionally oriented lexical competence has become the subject of scientific research by foreign researchers. Thus, Keiby Caro in the study "Lexis, Lexical Competence and Lexical Knowledge: A Review" examines in detail the concepts of vocabulary, lexical competence and activates lexical knowledge in accordance with the communicative purpose, interlocutor and social context [4]. Piyapong Laosrirattanachai and

Wannakarn Likitrattanaporn in their paper "A Case Study of English Lexical Competence and Performance involving Hospitality Students Conducting Tours" make an in-depth analysis of the gaps between lexical competence and speech productivity, focusing on the barrierless use of the communicative vocabulary and the communicative approach [5]. Ineta Luka in her article "Summative evaluation of online language learning course efficiency for students studying tourism and hospitality management" emphasizes the importance of intercultural competence in professionally oriented communication of future hotel and restaurant professionals along with communication and interactivity [6]. According to the participants of the DeSeCo project, communicative competence is one of the main key competences [7]. In turn, English lexical competence in professionally oriented communication of future hotel and restaurant professionals is also one of the key competencies of these professionals.

Despite the considerable attention of scientists to the outlined problem, the analysis of scientific sources showed that today there is no comprehensive study, dedicated to the disclosure of methodological approaches to the formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant professionals. All this gives grounds to assert that it is expedient to clearly define and substantiate the approaches and principles of target competence in speaking of future specialists in hotel and restaurant business. This determines the relevance of the selected topic.

3. Research aim and tasks

The paper aim is to determine methodological approaches to the formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future specialists in hotel and restaurant business.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

- 1) to outline the prerequisites for the use of the vocabulary, including terminology;
- 2) to choose approaches to the formation of professionally oriented English-language lexical competence in speaking in future specialists of hotel and restaurant business and to substantiate them;
- 3) to determine the principles of this process.

4. Materials and methods

The article uses theoretical research methods, in particular critical analysis of philosophical, pedagogical and psychological literature in order to determine the condition of research of the problem, its methodical and methodological foundations; study of normative documentation, programs of educational disciplines for generalization of theoretical data on the research problem; modeling of the educational process using the proposed methodological approaches and principles. A scientific observation of the organization of the process of teaching foreign languages for professional purposes in the Ukrainian HEIs was carried out. The interpretive-analytical method with the use of analysis (to reveal methodological approaches and principles to the forms of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant specialists), systematization and generalization (to provide recommendations and formulate conclusions) was used.

5. Research results and their discussion

Professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking of future hotel and restaurant professionals is interpreted as the ability to make their own oral statements in English on professional topics based on the correct selection and use of appropriate lexical units, including terms and terminological phrases. The main components of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking are: lexical knowledge, lexical skills (receptive and reproductive), lexical awareness.

Taking into account the results of research by Yarema I. [8], the prerequisites for the use of the vocabulary, including terminology, include:

- taking into account the stylistic features of the use of the professional vocabulary (the phenomena of synonymy, homonymy and polysemy, characteristic of oral professionally oriented communication of hotel and restaurant professionals);

- taking into account the semantic features of the use of the professional vocabulary (differences in the meanings of the lexical unit depending on the context; the semantic meaning of lexical units, which indicates the scope of use of the word and improves its memorization);

- taking into account the structural features of the vocabulary of the hotel and restaurant industry (one-component, two-component and multi-component terms);

- taking into account the morphological and syntactic features of the vocabulary of the hotel and restaurant sphere (methods of word formation, use of suffixes, prefixes, word formation);

- taking into account the peculiarities of the use of clichés, patterns, stereotypical lexical units, abbreviations and neologisms;

- taking into account the peculiarities of the development of linguistic and situational guess, which forms the associative base and promotes faster memorization of new lexical items;

- taking into account the role of the native language in teaching the professional vocabulary.

Speech learning, in turn, is part of the oral learning process, as the process involves learning both speak-

ing and listening. The processes of learning to speak and listen are closely intertwined in the process of communication, as the production of oral speech is impossible without the perception and understanding of oral speech by ear.

The communicative approach considers speaking as a component of oral speech.

The methodical and methodological organization of communication, including oral, in the educational context, is regulated by the communicative approach, focused on learning a language (in particular, a foreign language) through communication. The communicative approach to foreign language learning became relevant in the late 1960s, its principles were stemming from situational foreign language learning, which was the main approach to learning English as a foreign language in Britain. Based on the use of meaningful types of student learning activities, which was the basis of situational foreign language learning, the communicative approach emphasizes the choice of current situations of communication and organization of the process of competence formation in speech activities within these situations (in the context of our study - dominant situations of communication of hotel and restaurant specialists). At the same time, experts in English language teaching methods emphasized the functional and communicative potential of the language and believed that the formation of communicative competence in general is a priority of learning English as a foreign language, much more important than the formation of certain language skills, especially grammatical structures [9].

In connection with the trends of learning English as a foreign language, British linguists H. Stern [10], C. Brumfit [11] proposed an analysis of language in its functional and communicative aspects, which emphasized the system of meanings that accompany communicative language learning, and became the basic basis for the development of communicative learning of English as a foreign language.

H. Piepho [12] identified the correlation of language levels and their corresponding functions in the context of the communicative approach to foreign language learning (Table 1).

Table 1

Levels of language and their corresponding functions in the context of the communicative approach (by G. Piepho)

Language level		Function
integrative		Language as an expression means
context		
Linguistic		Language as a semiotic system, and its mastery as a goal of the learning process
instrumental		

Thus, the scientist believes that at the integrative and semantic levels, language serves as a means of expression, while at the linguistic and instrumental levels, language functions as a semiotic system, in turn, the mastery of this language is the goal of the learning process.

Taking into account the results of the analysis, carried out by scientists in previous years, in modern methods of teaching foreign languages the communicative approach is based on the statement that successful foreign language teaching involves communication and this process is more important than competent use of

lexical units and grammatical structures, or mistakes correction [13].

The analysis of V. Vdovin's research [14], which identifies a number of trends relevant to teaching a foreign language in the communicative approach, identified features of the formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant professionals on the communicative approach:

- communicative orientation of all types of educational activities of future specialists in hotel and restaurant business;
- involvement of future specialists in hotel and restaurant business in the process of forming their professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking by analyzing and taking into account their educational needs, interests and abilities ("the whole person approach");
- presentation of educational and methodical materials on the situational-thematic or functional principle;
- prevalence of such types of educational activities of students as pair work, which involves dialogue and work in small and large groups, which involves polylogization;
- indulgent attitude to mistakes, made by students in the process of verbal activity;
- analysis of students' mistakes in the context of their nature and category.

Thus, the teacher motivates future hotel and restaurant professionals to actively participate in the proposed tasks by their interest in the presented topic, current problem and communicative situation of professionally oriented oral communication, thus influencing the effectiveness of their training within the presented topics, problems and communicative situations, as well as the effectiveness of activating the already studied material.

The organization of speaking practice in real situations of professionally oriented oral communication of hotel and restaurant specialists on the basis of authentic videos contributes to the formation of students' professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking; because practicing professionally oriented speaking in different contexts based on certain lexical units and speech clichés (formulas), students master new lexical units, including terminological ones, thus expanding their vocabulary [15]. Educational materials, used in the application of the communicative approach, are divided into three categories [9]:

- based on texts;
- based on tasks;
- based on realities.

As for text-based teaching materials, they are mostly textbooks and manuals, the structure of a typical section of which consists of a topic, a number of tasks for elaboration of the topic, situational speech practice, stimulated presentation of audio or video materials, tasks for listening or watching [9].

Task-based learning materials include a number of didactic games, including role-playing games and simulations, sets of learning cards, and materials, including visuals, for interactive communication in pairs and small groups.

Learning materials based on realities, taken "from life", serve as a motivating factor to involve students in

speaking. Such training materials may include authentic videos, visual materials, including photos, objects, souvenirs, symbols, magazines, newspapers, maps, etc. The use of realities can increase the efficiency of the process of learning new lexical items, by activating the mechanism of building associative connections.

Teachers influence students' motivation by transforming the audience or virtual learning space into a comfortable learning environment that provides support and stimulates students to learn by involving them in tasks that are personal in nature, their interests, cultural background; by the thematic and semantic factor - features of professional activity, dominant communicative situations of professionally oriented oral communication of hotel and restaurant specialists; by the factor of the level of complexity – the level of knowledge of a foreign language (in the context of our study – English); according to the prognostic factor of effectiveness, they contribute to students' success [16].

The effectiveness of the formation of lexical competence of students in speaking, along with the communicative approach, provides active cooperation of the subjects of this process, which is based on the interactive approach. The basis of the interactive approach to the formation of lexical competence in professionally oriented speaking is a concept of interactivity as the ability to constant active communicative interaction in the systems "student – student", "student – students", "students – students", "teacher – student", "teacher – students" in pairs, small and large groups in the form of conversations, discussions, debates, dialogues, business and role-playing games, situational modeling between subjects of the educational process or with appropriate learning tools (computer or other gadget) in the context of co-learning or mutual learning. B. Suresh [17] argues that in the process of mastering English by students on the basis of the interactive approach such factors as socio-economic status, educational institution, educational habits, motivation to achieve results, conditions for extracurricular learning, interests and intelligence do not have significant impact on the effectiveness of the educational process, and thus – on the educational achievements of students.

H. Brown and G. Yule believe that speaking is a demonstration of the ability to achieve pragmatic goals with other speakers through interactive discourse [18], which is a type of communicative activity that has different forms of expression and takes place within a certain communication channel using appropriate communicative strategies, speech clichés (formulas) and involving the mechanism of synthesis of cognitive, linguistic and extralinguistic factors that shape speech genres and speech acts [19].

Effective interactive interaction of students in the process of forming their lexical competence in speaking is provided by the use of interactive teaching methods, in particular: didactic games (role, business, simulations), group projects, presentation and discussion of group project results.

Blended learning plays an important role in the context of the interactive approach. The key characteristic of blended learning is the optimal combination of classroom learning and extracurricular learning, in particular independent work with the help of network tech-

nologies using video, audio and text materials, which allows to create situations of oral professional communication in the learning process [20].

Communicative and interactive approaches to teaching foreign languages emphasize the concentration of the learning process on the student's personality as an active participant in the learning process. In this way, a close connection between communicative and student-centered approaches is realized in the process of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future specialists of hotel and restaurant business.

The student-centered approach is also widely used in the teaching and learning of foreign languages in higher education institutions. The ideas of the student-centered approach, declared in the works of scientists [21], emphasize the shift of emphasis from the teaching process to the learning process, and accordingly, from the expert teacher to the student. The learning process itself, aimed at the result, is much more important than the content of learning. Thus, students develop autonomy in learning and take responsibility for the learning process and the results of their own learning. Levels of student autonomy involve some intervention by the teacher regarding the content of education and its organization. I. Zadorozhna [22], based on the results of the study by A. Cohen [23], outlined the levels of autonomy depending on the models of interaction: subject-object model, subject-subject model, object-subject model. Therefore, in the context of our study we will use the concept of conditionally complete autonomy, proposed by I. Zadorozhna, taking into account the specifics of students' education in HEIs [22], which provides for the independent determination of the boundary and ultimate goals of educational activities, taking into account the requirements of the program of the discipline, individual and educational needs of students and the possibility to consult with a teacher if necessary; independent realization of the set tasks; self-control and self-correction, evaluation of results; control of knowledge, skills and abilities, acquired by students, by the teacher. Conditionally full autonomy is provided by the flexible nature of the teacher's management of students' educational activities.

The application of the student-centered approach to the formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking for future specialists' of hotel and restaurant business involves the construction of the entire educational process on the results of analysis of educational needs and interests of students.

Another methodological concept that stems from the student-centered approach is problem-solving learning. Problem-based learning, using an arsenal of problems, questions and triggers, allows students to develop the ability to set their own learning goals, fill gaps in knowledge or understanding, the formation of necessary skills, abilities and competencies [24].

Researchers from the University of Glasgow [25] propose to use four learning strategies in the context of the student-centered approach: – increase student activity in developing relevant skills, abilities and competencies, transforming them from passive to active participants through projects, presentations, resource packages, software; – raising students' awareness of the learning pro-

cess and its results; – emphasis on the interaction between the participants of the educational process in the systems "teacher-student" and "student-student" in the process of working in pairs, small and large groups, role and business games, simulations; – emphasis on the formation of students' abilities to transfer acquired skills, abilities, strategies and competencies through mentoring practice. Formulating learning outcomes based on the student-centered approach, experts focus on the skills and competencies of students, rather than on the amount of learning material that students need to master or its content [26]. Substantiating the process of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future specialists of hotel and restaurant business on the basis of the student-centered approach, the teacher performs the roles of guide, facilitator, moderator and advisor.

The importance of building the process of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future specialists in hotel and restaurant business on the basis of the sociolinguistic approach is proved by the results of research by R. Brown [27], who believed that there is a direct relationship between the number of lexical units in the vocabulary of a communication subject and his/her cultural development.

The author of the concept of communicative competence D. Hymes [28] emphasized the importance of acquainting students, studying a foreign language, with the cultural norms and models of communicative behavior of native speakers.

The sociolinguistic approach emphasizes the understanding of social practices, in which communicative interaction takes place as important factors in effective communication [29]. Such social practices include taking into account gender stereotypes, which are stable ideas about the key characteristics of men and women: traits, qualities, abilities and behavior of persons of different sexes. These key characteristics are closely related to the gender roles, enshrined in the system of cultural norms in accordance with the functions of men and women in typical etiquette situations [30].

The structure of the process of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future specialists of hotel and restaurant business on the basis of the sociolinguistic approach consists of: communicative event, involving a certain time, place and conditions of communication, communicative environment (reproduction of the professional context in the academic environment), subject content communication in situations of professionally oriented oral communication of hotel and restaurant specialists, emotional coloring that influences the choice of an appropriate style and genre, subjects of communicative interaction, English as a language of communication of hotel and restaurant specialists in a globalized environment, target level of English for professional purposes.

Thus, discursive practices, organized within educational situations, involve the extensive use of such teaching methods as role and business games, simulations, situational modeling, projects, oral presentations with further discussion, which allow to immerse the student in the context of oral professional communication of professionals in hotel and restaurant business and to form

his/her perception and awareness of the communication process in educational situations not as a usual academic task or exercise, but as a real oral professionally oriented communication of hotel and restaurant professionals with its challenges, communicative successes and failures. Thus, the sociolinguistic approach emphasizes the use of communicators' appropriate communication strategies, speech clichés (formulas).

The results of a study, conducted on the material of Chinese, Korean, Japanese and American shows, allow us to conclude that a large number of cultural codes, as well as their violations, can be observed in the process of intercultural communication, in particular – in the media. Such violations are usually ignored by native speakers, but they are noticed by attentive viewers (readers) who are not native speakers [31]. Taking into account the results of the above study, we consider it important to increase the efficiency of the process of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant professionals based on the sociolinguistic approach to conduct a contrastive and comparative analysis of cultural codes relevant to oral professionally oriented communication of specialists in hotel and restaurant business using information about other cultures. Basing the process of forming professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant professionals on the principles of the sociolinguistic approach, the teacher plays the role of: a guide in the world of cultures of English-speaking countries and cultures of countries, many tourists regularly visit Ukraine from, organizer of communicative practices in typical situations of oral professionally oriented communication of specialists of hotel and restaurant business, facilitator, moderator.

From each of these approaches follow the corresponding principles of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future professionals in hotel and restaurant business. The list of principles that are universal for all analyzed approaches includes:

- the principle of situationality;
- the principle of communicative activity;
- the principle of communicative value;
- the principle of immersion.

We distinguish ones specific to the context of our study in a separate group of principles:

- taking into account the target level of proficiency in English for professional purposes in the process of reproducing the professional context in the academic environment;

- reliance on communicative strategies and speech clichés in accordance with the situations of professionally oriented oral communication of hotel and restaurant specialists;

- parallel activation of visual and auditory channels of information perception.

The communicative status of communicators has a direct impact on the effectiveness of a communicative act in relation to the motive and communicative purpose of communicators, the course of the communicative act, the type of communicative interaction (constructive of which is cooperative), the choice of language means, the choice of speech means (communication strategies,

speech clichés). The type of communicative status, namely rigid or variable, depends on the roles of communicators and their motivation for cooperation.

In the context of our study, special attention should be paid to initiative roles, which are divided into short-term and long-term. Initiative long-term role is called image, which with the use of communicative strategies of self-presentation is used to realize a certain communicative intention and achieve a certain communicative goal [32].

Adherence to the principle of immersion allows you to simultaneously implement the processes of formation of English lexical competence in speaking during the study of the discipline "Foreign language for professional purposes (English)" and the formation of professional competencies during the study of the subject content of hotel and restaurant business (taking into account the results of research by S. Barsuk [33]). Implementation of the principle of immersion in the study of future specialists in hotel and restaurant business as disciplines "Foreign language (English)", "Foreign language (for professional purposes (English))" and professionally oriented disciplines in English will significantly increase the efficiency of the process of formation of English lexical competence in professionally oriented speaking in students.

The principle of taking into account the target level of English language proficiency in the professional direction in the process of reproducing the professional context in the academic environment emphasizes the conformity of the content of the formation of competence in future specialists in hotel and restaurant business, the level of complexity of educational material and the level of complexity of exercises and tasks to the level students' mastery in English and correspondingly to the level of formation of English lexical competence in speaking (in the context of our study we use the European recommendations for language education [34]).

The principle of reliance on communication strategies and speech clichés in accordance with the situations of professionally oriented oral communication of hotel and restaurant professionals involves the use of an arsenal, carefully selected and proposed by the teacher on the basis of authentic video clips, as well as selected by students in independent work, as speech supports, in the process of speaking.

The analysis of the methodology of formation of professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking in future hotel and restaurant specialists is insufficient. This may be the subject of further research. A promising area of further research is the study of the formation of professionally oriented foreign language lexical competence in reading, listening and writing in future specialists in hotel and restaurant business.

6. Conclusions

The analysis of the basic approaches has been carried out and the principles, on which the process of formation of English lexical competence in professionally oriented speaking at future experts of hotel and restaurant business is based, have been defined:

1. The following prerequisites for the use of the vocabulary, including terminological, as taking into account: stylistic features of the professional vocabulary,

semantic features of the professional vocabulary, structural features of the vocabulary of the hotel and restaurant sphere, morphological and syntactic features of the vocabulary of the hotel and restaurant sphere, features of using templates, stereotypical lexical units, abbreviations and neologisms, features of development of linguistic and situational guess, the role of the native language in the teaching of the professional vocabulary have been determined.

2. The efficiency of the formation of professionally oriented English-language lexical competence in speaking in future specialists of hotel and restaurant business on the basis of communicative, interactive, student-centered, sociolinguistic approaches has been proved. Communicative competence, including professionally oriented English lexical competence in speaking, which is its component, plays the role of leading key competences in the structure of foreign language professional competence of future hotel and restaurant professionals. The use of interactive teaching methods ensures effective interaction of students in the process of forming their lexical competence in

speaking. Blended learning plays an important role in the context of the interactive approach. In formulating learning outcomes based on the student-centered approach, the focus is on students' skills and competencies, rather than on the amount of learning material that students should master or its content. On the basis of the sociolinguistic approach, the creation of educational situations for the purpose of reproduction of scenarios of professionally oriented communication in typical situations of oral English-speaking professionally oriented communication of experts of hotel and restaurant business has been provided.

3. The principles of formation of professionally oriented communication of hotel and restaurant specialists have been substantiated. Predicting the components of situational position, which form the basis of typical communicative situations, predictive maps of situational positions have been made, which serve to create a list of typical communicative situations that will be practiced in the academic environment during the formation of English lexical competence in professionally oriented speaking of future hotel and restaurant specialists.

References

1. Vorobets, A. (2020). The concept of "lexical competence" in modern methodology of teaching foreign languages. *Germanic Philology Journal of Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University*, 822, 24–35. doi: <http://doi.org/10.31861/gph2020.822.24-35>
2. Polianichko, O. D. (2020). components of contents of lexic competence of future history teachers. *Transcarpathian Philological Studies*, 2 (13), 143–146. doi: <http://doi.org/10.32782/tps2663-4880/2020.13-2.29>
3. Mykytenko, N. O., Kotlovskiy, A. M. (2018). Intercultural communication as a prerequisite of building foreign professional and communicative competence of prospective specialists of non-philological specialties. *Pedahohichnyi almanakh*, 39, 75–84.
4. Caro, K., Mendinueta, N. R. (2017). Lexis, Lexical Competence and Lexical Knowledge: A Review. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 8 (2), 205–213. doi: <http://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.0802.01>
5. Laosrirattanachai, P., Likitrattanaporn, W. (2018). A Case Study of English Lexical Competence and Performance involving Hospitality Students Conducting Tours, 11 (4): *International Humanities, Social Sciences and arts*, 1557–1174.
6. Luka, I. (2018). Summative evaluation of online language learning course efficiency for students studying tourism and hospitality management. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 26 (4), 446–465. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1108/qa-04-2018-0051>
7. Definition and Selection of Key Competencies (2003). Contributions to the Second DeSeCo Symposium. Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/35070367.pdf>
8. Yarema, I. A. (2013). The linguistic peculiarities of formation English language lexical competence in metallurgists' professionally oriented speaking. *Visnyk KNLU. Series "Pedagogy and Psychology"*, 22, 63–71.
9. Richards, J. C., Rodgers, T. S. (2001). *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 270. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511667305>
10. Stern, H. H. (1996). *Fundamental Concepts of Language Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 582.
11. Brumfit, C. (1985). *Communicative Methodology in Language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 166.
12. Piepho, H. E. (1981). Establishing objectives in the teaching of English. *The Communicative Teaching of English: Principles and an exercise Typology*. London: Longman, 8–23.
13. Zardini, M. C., Barnabe, F. H. L. (2013). How to Improve the Speaking Skills through the Communicative Approach. *Dialogos Pertinentes Revista Científica de Letras*, 9 (2), 27–43.
14. Vdovin, V. V. (2007). Komunikatyvnyi pidkhd yak optymalnyi zasib vyvchennia inozemnoi movy u VNZ. *Visnyk Natsionalnoho universytetu «Lvivska politekhnika»*, 586, 15–20.
15. Savignon, S. J. (1983). *Communicative Competence: Theory and Classroom Practices*. Texts and Contexts in Second Language Learning. Massachusetts, 322.
16. Lightbown, P., Spada, N. (2013). *How Languages are Learned*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 257.
17. Suresh, B. (2011). *The Effect of Interactive Approach Model in Teaching English as Second Language: An Experimental Study*. Lambert Academic Publishing, 200.
18. Brown, H. D., Yule, G. (1999). *Teaching the spoken Language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 162.
19. Batsevych, F. S. (2006). *Vstup do lnhvistychnoi henealohii*. Kyiv: Vydavnychiy tsentr «Akademiiia», 248.
20. Friesen, N. (2012). Report: Defining Blended Learning. Available at: https://www.normfriesen.info/papers/Defining_Blended_Learning_NF.pdf Last accessed: 13.06.2016
21. Rogers, C. R. (1983). *As a Teacher, Can I Be Myself? Freedom to Learn for the 80's*. Ohio: Charles E. Merrill Publishing Company, 312.
22. Zadorozhna, I. P. (2012). *Teoretyko-metodychni zasady orhanizatsii samostiinoi roboty maibutnikh uchyteliv z ovolodinnia anhlomovnoiu komunikatyvnoiu kompetentsiieiu*. Kyiv, 440.

23. Cohen, A. D.; Hurds, S., Lewis, T. (Eds.) (2008). Speaking Strategies for Independent Learning: Focus on Pragmatic Performance. Language Learning. Language Learning Strategies in Independent Settings. Cromwell Press, 119–140. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21832/9781847690999-009>
24. Boud, D., Feletti, G. (1997). The Challenge of Problem Based Learning. London: Kogan Page, 344. doi: <http://doi.org/10.4324/9781315042039>
25. Hussain, S., Abbasi, Q. H., Ansari, I. S., Qadir, J., Imran, M. A. (2019). Online Interactive Tools to Support Student Centred Learning in Large Classes. University of Glasgow. Available at: <http://eprints.gla.ac.uk/179775/> Last accessed: 20.07.2019
26. Module and Programme Design. UCD Centre for Teaching and Learning. Course Design. Available at: <https://www.ucd.ie/teaching/resources/moduleandprogrammedesign/> Last accessed: 03.08.2019
27. Brown, R. (1986). Social Psychology. New York: The Free Press, 704.
28. Hymes, D.; Gumperz, J., Hymes, D. (Eds.) (1972). Models of the interaction of language and social life. Directions in sociolinguistics: The ethnography of communication. New York: Holt, Rhinehart&Winston, 35–71.
29. Long, M. H.; Long, M. (Ed.) (2005). Methodological Issues in Learner Needs Analysis. Second language needs analysis. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 19–76. Available at: <http://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511667299.002>
30. Batsevych, F. S. (2004). Osnovy komunikativnoi linhvistyky. Kyiv: Vyd. tsentr «Akademiia», 342.
31. Hinkel, E. (Ed.) (1999). Culture in Second Language Teaching and Learning. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 250.
32. Selivanova, O. O. (2011). Osnovy teorii movnoi komunikatsii. Cherkasy: Vydavnytstvo Chabanenko Yu. A., 350.
33. Barsuk, S. L. (2013). Suchasni pidkhody ta pryntsyipy navchannia anhliiskoi movy studentiv vyshchlykh navchalnykh zakladiv. Zb. nauk. pr. Pedagogichni nauky, 64, 392–339.
34. Nikolaieva, S. (Ed.) (2003). Zahalnoievropeiski rekomendatsii z movnoi osvity: vyvchennia, vykladannia, otsiniuvannia. Kyiv: Lenvit, 273.

Received date 26.08.2021

Accepted date 24.09.2021

Published date 30.09.2021

Iryna Skril, PhD, Department of Foreign Languages, Lviv Polytechnic National University, S. Bandery str., 12, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013
E-mail: iryna.skril@gmail.com